

PREPARATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS EMPLOYING MATRIX SUPERPLASTICITY EFFECT

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Solid state method of composite material fabrication in matrix superplasticity regime seems very promising as it ensures sufficient level of interaction and bonding between fibre and matrix at relatively low flow stresses and temperatures. With the aim of farther development of the method several questions were studied such as: transition to superplasticity regime of a titanium alloy matrix, interaction kinetics between the matrix and B(S,C) reinforcing fibres, fibre-matrix interface structure, mechanical properties at different temperatures.

The optimal deformation velocities were selected at which enhanced flow of matrix layers occurred around the indented fibre and which greatly assisted matrix fibre interaction processes.

The performed investigation allowed to establish technological parameters of composite material fabrication in superplastic regimes of matrix and on this basis recommendations are given for industrial applications.

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of solid state interaction reactions between fibre material and matrix showed that successful obtaining of fibre-reinforced composite greatly depends on the plasticity parameters of interacting components /1/.

To imitate matrix flowing processes around the fibre hard hemisphere indenting experiments were carried out in metals and alloys with different plastic properties /2/.

Several types of material distribution profiles were found around the indenter. In metals with conventional plasticity (aluminium lead) the profiles have edges with downward slope (Fig.1)

Fig.1. Indenting process in different cases:
a) conventional plasticity
b) volume superplasticity
c) local superplasticity near the indenter

while in superplastic alloys (63% Sn-37% Pb and 78% Zn-22Al) flow conditions were such that material was ejected from beneath the indenter and upheaved around it (Fig.1b). The height and width of such upheavals reach about $0.1d$ (d -the indenter diameter).

This type of profile is especially developed when the alloys are cast (Fig.1c). Probably in this case superplastic state is received only locally as a result of grain refinement in the deformed region around the indenter. Deprived of the possibility of deformation in side direction where superplasticity is not attained, the matrix flows in upward direction.

According to the obtained data when matrix foils and fibres are pressed together the following cases can be met.

When superplasticity conditions are sustained during composite preparation process upheavals are formed near the indented fibres and as a result the first contact of matrix foils is accomplished in the fibre vicinity and pockets are trapped at the fibre-matrix interface.

Fig.2. Kinetics of fibre indenting process in superplastic (solid line) and conventional plasticity (broken line) cases

Another situation arises when matrix is not in superplastic regime. In this case matrix foils contact each other far away from fibres (Fig.2, broken lines) and because of downward slope at interface pockets can not be avoided. In conventional technology to improve the bonding conditions high pressures are applied but this is accompanied by severe damage of fibres.

Thus the preliminary experiments had indicated the advantages of superplastic regime in composite preparation process. They also outlined some technological parameters such as distance between fibres (about $0.2-0.8d$) foil thickness $1-2d$ which gave the optimal volume fraction of fibres about 20-50%.

The aim of this work was to use the obtained data for preparing composite material from titanium alloy and boron fibres.

The reinforcement of titanium alloys with boron fibres is greatly hindered by active chemical matrix-fibre interaction at high temperatures used in conventional technology.

Coating of boron fibres with SiC layers is only a partial solution of interaction problem and more effective measure must be the lowering of the composite preparation temperature. For the latter cause preparation in superplastic regimes is apparently most promising.

EXPERIMENTAL

A titanium alloy containing 3.5% Al and 1.5% Mn was used as matrix material. Boron fibres with $d = 100 \mu\text{m}$ were coated by $2-3 \mu\text{m}$

thick SiC. To obtain matrix foils of optimum thickness for given fibre diameter hot working at 950°C in superplastic regime was used. Sandwich type samples were compressed at 920°C in a special stage of high temperature optical microscope "Kirgizstan" with maximum pressures about 180 MPa. The employed deformation rate was $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-1}-10^{-2}$. That was regarded as practically realizable: the time of compressing was about 3-6 min. Mechanical properties were measured on the same equipment. Structure of the composite was investigated on scanning electron microscope with microanalyzer. The typical microstructures are reproduced on Fig. 3a,b. The fibres are practically undamaged in contrast to conventional case.

No voids were found along the fibres metallografically (Fig. 3b)

Fig. 3. a) Microstructure of fibre-reinforced sample
 * b) Along fibre section

The electron probe showed no changes in chemical composition at the interface for usual times of preparation (3-6 min) and only after artificial prolongation of the process above 10 minutes the interaction zone widened to 2-3 mm thickness and diffusional interchange of silicon and titanium atoms was found by local chemical analysis. As a result transition zone must contain silicon and titanium carbides [3].

It must be noted that no structural changes of matrix were observed around the fibres (Fig. 3a) which is typical for superplastic behaviour.

The investigation of tensile properties in wide temperature range showed higher strength of samples prepared in superplastic regime.

It was found that tensile strength values were close to theoretical for this two-phase composite (Fig. 4). The examination of fracture surfaces of tensile specimens showed that fibres were tightly embedded in matrix (Fig. 5)

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced samples (20% SiC)
 1. Theoretical curve
 2. Superplastic regime
 3. Conventional regime

Fig. 5. Structure surface of fibre-reinforced samples prepared in superplastic regime.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The deformation rate which was employed in the present investigation although reasonable from practical point of view is too fast for superplasticity, which for the given material at 920°C is about $\dot{\epsilon} \approx 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for tensile deformation. But it should be noted that the regime depends on the deformation mode and for three axial stress state superplasticity is achieved at lower deformation rates.

It is highly probable that stressed state near fibres in compressed composite is close to three axial. Besides the matrix deformation rate around fibre can be two or three times higher than compression rate. All these possibilities lead to a conclusion that the matrix can be in superplastic regime at the interface. But the best proof of this presumption is the fact itself of the preparation of high quality composite at lower temperature ($t=920^\circ\text{C}$) and pressure ($p=10 \text{ MPa}$) and shorter time (3-6min) than in conventional technology where corresponding values are: $t=1000^\circ\text{C}$, $P=150+200 \text{ MPa}$, $t=15-20 \text{ min}$.

Lower temperature and shorter time allowed to reduce also the intensity of diffusional interaction at the interface while superplastic flow around fibres improved the contact and welding conditions of the two components.

Thus it can be concluded that preparation of composites in superplastic regime is advantageous not only technologically (lower temperatures and pressures) but also from the point of view of composite structure when chemical interaction problem must be solved at phase interfaces.

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